

Neural Correlates of Human Rhythm Interaction and Experience

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ABSTRACT

Sensorimotor synchronisation to music, such as dancing, exists as a cross-cultural phenomenon with informational, affective, perceptual, and health-related benefits. In-depth understanding of these interactions can maximise their impact across health and entertainment contexts. While neuroscience has advanced insight into rhythm and music interactions, most research has focused on internal brain representation and computational models of perception, often relying on passive listening paradigms. These approaches overlook active engagement and subjective experience, a key motivational component behind rhythmic interactions. As a result, realism and ecological validity remain limited. This study addresses that gap by exploring neural entrainment in an active synchronisation paradigm and assessing its potential to predict user experience. Participants synchronised tapping with an auditory rhythm generated either by another participant or a computer while rating experience across multiple dimensions, including pleasure and flow. EEG-based neural features were extracted, analysed and correlated with user experience. These features included neural entrainment measures (via discrete Fourier transforms, auto-correlation, beta band modulation amplitudes) as well as non-entrainment related band power features. Results showed that partner type influenced experience: human interactions elicited higher flow and marginally higher arousal compared to non-adaptive computer conditions. Neural entrainment patterns distinguished between simple and complex rhythmic conditions, with modulation amplitudes correlating with and predicting flow experience, outperforming behavioural synchrony. In contrast, entrainment features were less predictive of pleasure, where non-modulated band power features performed better. Overall, neural entrainment demonstrated promise in characterising interactive rhythmic conditions and predicting experience.

1. Introduction

In a multi-modal world, synchronisation with our surroundings plays a key role in structuring our environment (Repp and Su (2013); Leman Marc (2016)). Sensorimotor synchronisation (SMS) reflects the synchronisation of motion to a predictable external stimulus, particularly in a musical context (Pressing (1999)). This study focuses on SMS primarily in rhythmic interactions. In musical or rhythmic synchronisation, the rewarding effect of being adequately locked to the beat is the main driving force towards this synchrony (Schaefer and Overy (2015); Smykovskiy et al. (2023)). Beyond emotional rewards, SMS enhances information exchange, strengthens affective bonds between individuals (Hoehl et al. (2020); Leman Marc (2016)), and extends to applications in health and medicine. SMS applications contribute to emotional and cognitive improvements and aid in rehabilitation for disorders such as Parkinson's disease, autism spectrum disorder, and stroke (Dyer (2017); Nombela et al. (2013); Thaut and McIntosh (2014); Bernardi et al. (2017); Koshimori et al. (2023); LaGasse et al. (2024)). Consequently, health and entertainment applications drive efforts to refine rhythmic interactions, enhancing immersion, enjoyment (Grandjean et al. (2008); Leman (2007)), in turn further enhancing engagement, entrainment, and associated benefits. However, refining these interactions requires an in-depth understanding of the underlying mechanisms and user experiences. This study aims to provide insight into these interactions by implementing a human-rhythm interaction paradigm with a focus on characterising neural EEG features, detailing multiple aspects of neural entrainment to capture user experience.

Physical behavioural synchrony can provide partial insight into felt experience and perception, by reflecting both structural grouping of the rhythm into beat and meter precepts (Jacoby et al. (2024)) and subjective experience during music synchronisation by the manner and speed of body motion (Saarikallio et al. (2013)). Fast, spread-out and

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complex movement patterns can correlate with self-reported positive affect and reflect general motivation in behaviour. In human-human interactions, motion synchrony, stability, and accuracy influence perceived affect and performance fluency (Tschacher et al. (2014); Paul Reddish and Whitehouse (2020); Stupacher (2019)), highlighting the key role of perception-action coupling in connecting flow experience with musical activities.

However, behaviour-based experience prediction is influenced by external factors such as social context, synchronisation partner (Kirschner and Tomasello (2009); Cui et al. (2022)), or even physical limitations in synchronising to the stimulus. The commonly used fixed metronome in human-computer interactions further amplifies this bias, reducing ecological validity, and limiting realism (Cheng et al. (2022); Nozaradan et al. (2016b)), emphasising the need for variable paradigms with adaptive interactions (Walton et al. (2018)) along with in-depth consideration of the impact of the rhythmic partner's adaptability. Other factors such as difficulty and challenge further co-modulate experience and obscure the relationship between behaviour and felt emotion (Stupacher (2019); Engeser and Rheinberg (2008)). Together, these biases underscore the need for a more refined framework to assess human-rhythm interactions and evaluate experience beyond behavioural markers, accounting for partner realism.

Given the limitations of behaviour-based experience prediction, an alternative approach is to examine neural activity, which provides a direct window into cognitive and perceptual processes during synchronisation (Bondar' and Fedotchev (2000)). During rhythmic synchronisation, the brain continuously optimizes an internal model of the outside world (Mumford (1992)), reducing prediction errors in alignment (Friston (2005, 2010)) and enabling efficient event processing (Koelsch et al. (2019)). This internal representation of rhythms and the mechanisms underlying behavioural synchrony highlight neural entrainment - the alignment of neural oscillations to external rhythmic stimuli - as the core drive for the interaction (Rosso et al. (2023); Haegens and Zion Golumbic (2018); Lakatos et al. (2019)). Neural entrainment thus provides a unique perspective on rhythmic interactions and their experience, offering insights into multiple facets of sound encoding, cognition, and perception (Obleser and Kayser (2019); Doelling and Assaneo (2021)).

Frequency-domain analysis (frequency tagging) captures neural entrainment by detecting rhythmic EEG responses to the external stimuli. This can manifest as the presence of rhythm frequencies in EEG spectral components (via DFT or autocorrelation) or as band-based power modulations (Nozaradan et al. (2012); Nozaradan (2014); Fujioka et al. (2012, 2015)). These responses may stem from 1) the periodic repetition of transient neural activities related to the processing rhythmic sequences or 2) the synchronised activity of neurons entraining to the periodic repetition or modulation of a stimulus – both mechanisms are supported in literature (Chemin et al. (2018); Haegens and Zion Golumbic (2018); Draganova et al. (2002); Galambos et al. (1981)).

Crucially, neural entrainment has been shown to track cortical activity related to higher-level perceptual processes (Chemin et al. (2018, 2014); Nozaradan et al. (2015, 2017)). Attention and cognition modulate neural activity associated with unaccented auditory streams, influencing both the evoked stimulus responses and the spectral power associated with the attended or an imagined stimuli (Breska and Deouell (2017); Nobre and van Ede (2018); Large et al. (2015)). Consequently, brain entrainment serves as a mechanism which shapes and modulates perception, effectively creating a *rhythmic mode of perception* that directs focus towards specific stimuli (Patel and Iversen (2014); Celma-Miralles et al. (2021); Martin et al. (2007); Fujioka et al. (2015)). Thus, neural entrainment provides effective insight into how cognition shapes rhythmic perception through top-down modulation.

Conversely, observing neural entrainment may then elucidate an individual's perception or overall experience during an interaction. This is supported by research linking physiological activity to human emotion and experience (Shu et al. (2018)), particularly through brain activity (Liu et al. (2021); Cui et al. (2022); see reviews therein). Within music evoked emotion classification, models rely on EEG markers from local or cross-electrode components in spectral band activity (alpha, beta, gamma, & delta) (Cui et al. (2022)) or the time-domain features (Liu et al. (2021)). These models incorporate general statistical properties (e.g., mean, standard deviation) alongside more refined features such as (differential) entropy, power spectral density, region connectivity, and fractal analysis to enhance prediction accuracy (Lin et al. (2010); Moon et al. (2020)). Nevertheless, applying these models in real-life conditions remains challenging. EEG-datasets are limited, and emotional arousal is often attained using passive perception paradigms (Avramidis et al. (2021); Zainab and Majid (1970); Thammasan et al. (2016) and datasets: Koelstra et al. (2012); Duan et al. (2013); Zheng and Lu (2015)). Consequently, little data exists on imagined or active music/rhythm interactions (Almudena et al. (2020)), and used paradigms may not accurately reflect real-world scenarios, where individuals naturally engage with music and actively partake in interactions (Becker (2001); Foster Vander Elst et al. (2021)).

Figure 1: Hypothesised modulation of entrainment. Neural entrainment changes from low (blue) to high (yellow) experience, evaluated at fractions of the metronome frequency (f_m).

1.1. Goals and aims

To address the discussed limitation of passive interactions and ecological validity, the present study aims to advance the characterisation of neural entrainment and classify emotional experience within an active synchronisation paradigm. Specifically, it explores the potential of neural features - neural entrainment in particular - as a marker and predictor of perceived rhythms and emotions such as pleasure and flow, while contrasting human-human versus human-computer interactions and their impact on experience. Accuracy of the attained prediction models of experience are compared to a baseline model using behavioural synchrony, and another using a naïve subset of non-modulated band-based features. Task complexity was additionally modulated between evaluated conditions to vary the levels of challenge. The study aims to validate the following hypotheses:

H1: Neural entrainment can serve as a marker of rhythm interaction experience, where the magnitude of spectral neural magnitudes correlates with observed experience.

We hypothesise that neural entrainment, beyond behaviour synchrony, serves as a neural representation of this same synchrony to the outside world and further reflects experience. We expect neural activity, reflecting both heard stimuli and performed tasks, to be modulated by its experience, see Figure 1. Increases in experience should align with enhanced neural entrainment at the metronome (f_m) and task frequencies ($f_m/2, f_m/3$), mirroring studies on behaviour-experience correlation. Following theories of entrainment and affordance (Leman (2007)), attention is given to the subharmonic ($f_m/6$), which relate to overarching Gestalt concepts of rhythm perception (Coulon et al. (2024)). These elements help to contextualize rhythmic interactions within broader perceptual structures, offering deeper insight into their impact on user experience.

H2: Neural entrainment can equal or surpass behavioural synchrony in experience prediction.

Compared to behavioural markers, neural entrainment may be less influenced and masked by external factors such as social contexts or reduced synchronisation capabilities, making it a potentially more reliable and unbiased representation of rhythmic interaction and user experience.

H3: Experience in a non-adaptive human-computer interactions differs from human-human interactions.

The lack of adaptability and realism in metronome-based interactions may result in a noticeably distinct experience compared to human-human synchronisation. Identifying these contrasts will reinforce prior findings on the importance of adaptive, dynamic interactions in fostering meaningful experiences.

This research thus introduces a novel approach by employing an active paradigm for rhythm- and music- based interactions to explore emotion and different parameters of human interaction like task complexity and partner realism, where previous studies primarily relied on passive paradigm to evoke emotion. Additionally, this study uniquely explores neural entrainment as a key component in characterizing both neural features and user experience within an active setting.

2. Materials and Methods

A total of 20 participants (reported genders: 9 males, 11 females), aged between 21 and 30 years ($M = 24.7$ $SD = 2.5$), took part in the experiment. Their highest level of education ranged from secondary school to PhD, and their musical training, as assessed by the Goldsmiths Musical Sophistication Index, ranged from 7 to 46 ($M = 24.8$, $SD = 13.9$). Participants registered in pairs with a familiar rhythmic partner to ensure comfortable interaction (Latif et al. (2014)). They had no prior knowledge of the experimental procedure and had not previously participated in a similar synchronisation paradigm.

The analysis considered a final sample size N of 19 participants, as one participant was excluded due to EEG-artefacts and issues with fluency of conducting the interaction experiment. The sample size mirrors comparable research on active and passive paradigms for neural entrainment ($N = 14$, in Fujioka et al. (2015)), $N = 16$ in Nozaradan et al. (2016a), $N = 21$ in Morillon and Baillet (2017)). After receiving a general description and an informational letter about the study, participants gave informed consent while observing privacy rights. The study was approved by the ethics committee of the faculty of arts and philosophy of Ghent University (Belgium) on the 16th of January of 2023 [2023-31] and was conducted in accordance with relevant laws and their ethical guidelines.

2.1. Pre-questionnaire

Participants completed a pre-experiment questionnaire that assessed their relationship with their rhythmic partner, as well as their same-day caffeine intake, their musical background, and medical history, including current medications, and any diagnosed condition that might affect concentration or attention. All participants indicated to be right-handed and reported no history of hearing impairment, which was confirmed via on-site hearing screening (hearWHO application on Sennheiser HDA 300 headphones). Hearing scores ranged from 80 to 100 ($M = 95$, $SD = 8.4$). Additionally, all participants reported normal or corrected-to-normal vision. Self-reported medical background revealed two participants with concentration or attention related conditions, and two participants on medications that could affect attention or concentration. Eight participants reported caffeine intake prior to the experiment. Musical background was assessed using the Goldsmiths Musical Sophistication Index (Müllensiefen et al. (2014)), to account for task proficiency. Partner relationships were evaluated through two 5-item Likert scale questions: "How often do you meet with your musical partner?" (Van Kerrebroeck et al. (2023)) and "Which picture best describes your relationship with this person?" (Aron et al. (1992)). These pre-experiment responses were recorded but excluded from the analysis as they did not impact post-experiment experience after z-scoring (Appendix A).

2.2. Experimental paradigm

The paradigm involved two participants synchronising their tapping with a drum kick rhythm generated by their rhythmic partner during a 190-second interaction. This rhythmic partner was either the other participant, located in a separate booth, or a computer-generated fixed rhythm - though this information was not disclosed to the participants. In each interaction, both participants and the computer performed a rhythmic task based on either a binary or ternary rhythm, as instructed beforehand. Each rhythm was constructed from a 6-beat metronome, divided into two (binary) or three (ternary) parts of equal duration, as illustrated in the left panel of Figure 2 by the white (6 beats), blue (binary), and yellow (ternary) lines, respectively. Regardless of the tapping task (binary or ternary), the first beat for both participants needed to align with each other and an initially presented metronome. However, since the first shared beat was not aurally emphasized, binary and ternary rhythms primarily differed in tapping rates. Initially, the required tapping frequencies were communicated via an auralised 6-beat metronome (3.75 Hz, 225 bpm), which dictated a ternary rhythm (1.875 Hz, 112.5 bpm) and a binary rhythm (1.25 Hz, 75 bpm), as shown in white, yellow, and blue in Figure 2, right panel. The full 6-beat measure lasted 1.6 seconds (0.625 Hz). Participants were made clear that the main goal of each interaction was a good, shared performance with their partner while performing their task, and that they may have to slow down or speed up to stay together. Regardless, for human-human interactions, a natural drift in performed tapping frequencies is expected due to the absence of a fixed reference.

The rhythmic tasks were paired between participants to create four distinct rhythm interactions: two matched "simple" conditions (binary-binary and ternary-ternary), where both participants performed the same task, and two poly-rhythmic "complex" conditions (binary-ternary and ternary-binary), where participants perform complementary tasks. Both simple and complex conditions were included to introduce variation in task difficulty and to elicit a broader range of reported experiences. Furthermore, did complex interactions enable the induction of perceived entrainment by presenting affordances for synchrony.

Figure 2: Visual task illustration. Stimuli presented in booth A during the 3_2 (left) and 2_3(right) conditions prior to the main tapping interaction.

Condition	Partner	Booth A		Booth B	
		Sound	Task	Sound	Task
2_2	PH	Pad B	Binary	Pad A	Binary
2_3	PH	Pad B	Ternary	Pad A	Binary
3_2	PH	Pad B	Binary	Pad A	Ternary
3_3	PH	Pad B	Ternary	Pad A	Ternary
2_2	PC	PC	Binary	Pad A	Binary
2_3	PC	PC	Ternary	Pad A	Binary
3_2	PC	PC	Binary	Pad A	Ternary
3_3	PC	PC	Ternary	Pad A	Ternary
3_3 test-retest	PC	PC	Ternary	Pad A	Ternary

Table 1

Overview of interaction conditions as evaluated in the main experiment. *Partner* reflects the partner with whom the participant in booth A interacted. *Sound* columns indicate the auralised sound within each booth as generated by a sample pad (Pad) or computer (PC). For the interactions with **PC**, the sound in booth A was replaced with a **PC** rhythm that mirrored the task in booth B but maintained a fixed tempo, while booth B still heard the physical taps from booth A. *Task* reflects the required task by the participant situated in both booths.

When synchronisation occurs, the first beat of the binary and ternary rhythms aligns, creating a single aligned percept per measure. These alignments may increase the drive for successful interaction, enhancing motivation and performance (Leman (2007)). Consequently, within neural activity, an additional spectral component is expected at the 6-beat interval, i.e., 1.6 seconds. The combination of rhythmic variability (binary/ternary) and partner type (human or computer) resulted in nine conditions evaluated in this paper (Table 1), including an additional test-retest measurement for the 3_3 **PC** interactions. Auralisation conditions are denoted as either **PH** or **PC**. In the **PH**(human) conditions, participants in both rooms heard only their human partner's tapping as reference. The existence of a computer partner was not disclosed to participants to maintain the illusion of interacting with a human.

2.3. Stimuli and tapping recordings

The taps from both participants and PC were auralised using Alesis 4-Samplepads, which played drum-samples at a comfortable listening level. The auralised stimuli depend on the partner involved (PC or PH) (see Table 1). Figure 3 shows a schematic of the two-booth setup, with conditional audio routing indicated by a black box. For auralisation of performed taps by both participants and the computer to the other participant, a drum kick sample was used with a low-frequency content, ensuring optimal neural tracking of the beat, as recommended by Lenc et al. (2018). The sounds of both participants were recorded separately using an RME UCX Fireface soundcard. An additional trigger signal, not auralised to both participants, was recorded by both the sound card and EEG-equipment and allowed precise timestamping of the auditory onsets. Physical tapping onsets were reconstructed by applying a validated negative time shift to the auditory onsets.

Figure 3: Dual-booth experimental setup. Schematic of the interaction paradigm between two shielded booths (A & B), with conditional audio routing (centre). EEG was recorded exclusively in booth A.

2.4. System setup

Participants were seated separately in two electrically and acoustically shielded booths (A and B) and could neither see nor hear each other during the interactions. In booth A, participants sat in a reclining chair and were fitted with an EEG headcap and binaural tubal insert earphones (ER2). In booth B, participants sat upright and wore Sennheiser HDA 300 headphones for binaural audio presentation. Alesis 4-Samplepads, positioned below the participants' hands, registered their taps. Two monitors (60 Hz) displayed prompts and task instructions to each participant, as shown in Figure 3. Synchronisation during the experiment between presented visuals, auditory metronomes and PC taps was managed by Psychopy (Peirce et al. (2019)) by aligning audio sound card output to the first frame of the shown visuals. Resulting offsets between auditory and visual information remained at or below 1 frame (16.66 ms). EEG activity was recorded at 16 kHz using a Biosemi ActiveTwo system Biosemi (2025) with a 64-channel Ag/AgCl-sintered electrode montage following the 10-20 international layout. After EEG data collection in booth A across the nine conditions, participants switched booths, and the experiment was repeated.

Each interaction consisted of five parts (Figure 4). 1) **Task Description:** Participants received instructions for the upcoming task, including prompts to sit comfortably, relax their muscles, and restrict movement to their fingers and wrists. They were also asked to focus their gaze on a central cross and maintain this fixation throughout the interaction. Verbal reminders were provided between trials to encourage limited movement and further reduce muscle artefacts. 2) **Audio-Visual Illustration:** A visual illustration depicted the upcoming interaction (Figure 2), showing a metronome (white, top row), the participant's task (yellow, middle row), and the partner's task (blue, bottom row). Accompanying the image, a 20-second audio sample played, gradually introducing a woodblock metronome (white), followed by a finger snap (yellow) and drum kick (blue), leading to an example of the auralised full interaction task. 3) **Main Interaction:** The monitor displayed a white cross with rotating spheres that passed through it at the task-dependent binary or ternary rate (1.25 Hz or 1.875 Hz), guiding initial tapping. Depending on the condition (Table 1), the corresponding partner sound was auralised. In PC conditions, the computer-generated rhythm, which matches the Task of booth B, was presented in booth A. The luminance of the cross, shown identically in both booths, reflected performance - gradually increasing with accurate synchronisation and decreasing with poor performance (Appendix B). These luminance changes occurred slowly over multiple seconds to minimize visual EEG artefacts. 4) **Performance-based Interaction:** After 30 seconds, the spheres and metronome faded, leaving only the cross and auralised rhythm to guide participants. 5) **Post-interaction Questionnaire:** After the 190-second interaction, both participants completed a questionnaire assessing their overall sensation and experience in the past interaction (*Supplementary material 1*).

2.5. Post-experiment questionnaire

The post-experiment questionnaires assessed experienced flow, agency, self-other integration (SOI) Aron et al. (1992), and shared agency (Van Kerrebroeck et al. (2023)). Items from the Flow short scale on 'fluency of performance' and 'absorption by activity' (Engeser and Rheinberg (2008)) were combined and summed, and pleasure/arousal were

Figure 4: Experiment interaction timeline. Overview of interaction phases: (1) task description, (2) audiovisual interaction example, (3-4) main interaction, and (5) post-experiment questionnaire.

additionally included using the Affective slider (Betella and Verschure (2016)). These experience metrics were Z-scored for each participant ($z = (x - \mu)/\sigma$) to emphasise within-subject variations over absolute scores, where μ and σ represent the mean and standard deviation, respectively, per subject and experience metric. This normalisation aimed to account for potential influence of individual factors such as musical training, caffeine intake, and partner relationship on reported experience in agency, flow, pleasure, and arousal.

2.6. Localisers and training

Before the main experiment, localiser and training sessions were conducted. Localiser measurements, limited to booth A, identified electrode regions involved in motor activity (motor localiser) and auditory processing (auditory localiser) by using two separate interactions dedicated to a single mode (auditory or motor). In the motor localiser, participants tapped at a self-chosen fixed rate for 190 seconds without external auditory cues and absent visual information. In the auditory localiser, drum-kick samples were presented at a variable rate with uniformly distributed inter-beat intervals between 0.5 and 1.5 seconds for 150 seconds. Participants were also instructed to relax all muscles and avoid movement.

Training sessions familiarised participants with the interaction structure. These consisted of five blocks, mirroring the main experiment but limited to 90-second human-human interactions (**PH**). Conditions were trained in a fixed order (3_3, 2_2, 2_3, 3_2) with each condition practiced up to three times, depending on participants' preferences. While potential learning effects were acknowledged, this order was chosen to gradually increase complexity, maintain motivation and provide a standardised shared learning effect. Participants rarely reported performance improvements between the second and third training sessions for complex conditions, suggesting that the three sessions were sufficient to attain this effect - though further learning effects may still have occurred within the main experiment.

2.7. Data processing

Behavioural marker extraction and EEG preprocessing were performed in MATLAB® using the EEGLAB toolbox followed by statistical analyses in R and Python. The anonymised EEG measurement data and post-experiment responses, without subject specific properties on medical and personal background, were made available as a dataset on Zenodo (Van Ransbeek (2025)).

2.7.1. Behavioural performance markers

Behavioural synchrony was assessed based on booth A's tapping relative to the auditory signal presented there. Tap onsets were denoted as T_n , and beat onsets as B_n , with beats generated either by the human partner in booth B or by the computer. False-positive taps - those occurring within 100 ms of a prior tap - were excluded. Two synchronisation metrics were considered: relative phase angle and resultant vector length (Moens et al. (2014); Moumdjian et al. (2018)). As these metrics assume similar tap and beat frequencies, a theoretical beat sequence B_n^* was constructed for poly-rhythmic conditions to represent ideal tap timing for booth A under optimal synchrony. Intervals of consecutive beats B_n were segmented into their underlying 6-beat measures, and grouped according to the tapping task in booth A (binary, ternary), yielding B_n^* (see Figure 5). For the matched conditions (ternary-ternary and binary-binary), $B_n = B_n^*$.

Figure 5: Theoretical beat construction. Illustration of how the theoretical beat B_i^* is derived from available beats B_i for a 2_3 pattern.

The relative phase angle ϕ_n quantifies timing deviation between a tap onset T_n and the nearest reference beat B_n^* and its successor B_{n+1}^* , equation 1. Positive values indicate delayed taps; negative values indicate anticipatory ones:

$$\phi_n = 2\pi \left(\frac{T_n - B_n^*}{B_{(n+1)}^* - B_n^*} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$R = \left| \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \exp(i\phi_n) \right| \quad (2)$$

The Resultant vector length R measures the stability of the relative phase angle ϕ_n across taps (Equation 2), where N denotes the total number of taps. R ranges from 0 to 1, with higher values reflecting stronger synchrony. This was computed using the CircStats toolbox (Berens (2009)). As supplementary metric, mean asynchrony quantified the average temporal offset (in seconds) between each tap T_n and the nearest theoretical beat B_n^* , with higher values indicating greater delays.

2.7.2. EEG pre-processing

A unified preprocessing pipeline was used for both localisers and main interaction EEG data. For the main interactions, the first 30 seconds were excluded to remove visual and auditory artefacts from the metronome and spheres. In contrast, localiser data retained their full duration. EEG signals were downsampled to 512 Hz using *pop_resample* and high-pass filtered at 0.1 Hz (*pop_eegfiltnew()*) to remove slow drifts while preserving low-frequency activity relevant to 6-beat periodicities (0.625 Hz, Cheng et al. (2022)). Following the resampling frequency, synchronisation accuracy was not assessed below 2ms.

Bad channels were identified through visual inspection and Artifact Subspace Reconstruction (ASR) using *clean_artifacts()* with custom parameters ('FlatlineCriterion' 'OFF', 'Highpass' 'OFF' 'ChannelCriterion' 0.6 'LineNoiseCriterion' 'OFF' 'BurstCriterion' 5 'WindowCriterion' [], Chang et al. (2020)). On average, 4.3 (SD = 3.8) channels were identified as bad and interpolated per measurement using spherical interpolation based on the 10–20 layout. The resulting data was then re-referenced to the global channel average. EEG analysis targeted both auditory and motor responses, key elements of sensorimotor synchronisation (SMS). However, overlapping neural sources and muscle artefacts - especially during active motor tasks - complicate source-specific interpretations from auditory or motor responses (Frölich and Dowding (2018)). To address this, Independent Component Analysis (ICA, *pop_runica*) was applied, assuming source independence and non-Gaussian activity distributions (Bell and Sejnowski (1995); Makeig et al. (1995)). Resulting components were then classified using ICLabel (Pion-Tonachini et al. (2019)). Those with a

brain-probability score below 0.4 were deemed artefactual (e.g., eye blinks, muscle activity) and regressed out of the EEG activity.

2.7.3. Localiser Identification

For each auditory or motor localiser measurement, a single independent component (IC) was selected from the cleaned ICs (brain-probability > 0.4) that best represented, respectively, auditory or motor activity. The candidate ICs were evaluated on their variance contribution across all electrodes to the back-projected event-related potentials (ERP). For both localiser types epochs were extracted from -300 ms to 500 ms around either auditory or motor events, with baseline correction using a -100 to -50 ms interval. For each of the epoched ICs, its relative contribution to total variance was computed by the *percent variance accounted for* (pvaf, Fujioka et al. (2012); Cheng et al. (2022)). In it, the variance defined by originating from a single IC (back-projected EEG data) is considered relative to the original variance in the data, and limited to predefined window, associated with the performed localiser.

Motor localiser ICs were evaluated from -50 ms to 100 ms relative to tap onset, capturing both anticipatory and movement related tapping activity (Shibasaki and Hallett (2006); Pollok et al. (2003); Gerloff et al. (1998)). Alternatively, the auditory localisers focused on 50 ms-150 ms post-stimulus to encompass the N1-P2 complex, Näätänen and Picton (1987). For each individual two ICs were identified to reflect either motor or auditory localised activity. Selected auditory and motor ICs ranked in the top 3 of highest pvaf values within their relevant windows and among their respective competing ICs, and exhibited spatial topographies consistent with known auditory or motor sources (Cheng et al. (2022)).

Auditory ICs typically show symmetrical, centralized topographies due to bilateral stimulation of auditory cortices Cheng et al. (2022); Korzyukov et al. (1999). In contrast, motor localisers exhibit a left-lateralised pattern, consistent with contralateral activation during right-hand tapping Cheng et al. (2022). However the spatial precision of ICA is limited, (Cheng et al. (2022); Onton et al. (2006)), and a single IC can consist of multiple highly temporally dependent activity and individual ICs may capture multiple overlapping processes - such as prediction, evoked responses, and motor activity - if they are temporally and spatially correlated. Therefore, IC interpretations should be made cautiously.

2.8. Main interaction processing

Weights from the localisers were applied to the interaction data after artefact IC removal. The identified motor and auditory components were used to extract subject-specific time series for each interaction after similar non-brain component removal (brain-probability > 0.4). These time series are referred to as “AUD IC” and “MOT IC” in the following analyses for the respective auditory and motor identified component.

2.8.1. Frequency domain analysis

To analyse neural entrainment, both AUD IC and MOT IC were transformed into the frequency domain using the discrete Fourier transform (DFT) Frigo and Johnson (1998). However, since human-human interactions (**PH**) include non-isochronous timing of the auditory stimuli, EEG data were time-warped to align inter-beat intervals (IBIs) of B_n with those of the corresponding **PC** condition, following Chemin et al. (2018). This stretching allowed studying non-strictly-periodic rhythmic neural processes during acoustic rhythm perception and sensorimotor synchronisation. EEG data segments between beats B_n underwent linear interpolation to match the fixed IBIs: 0.800 s (1.25 Hz, 410 samples) for binary beats (2_2 and 2_3), and 0.533 s (1.875 Hz, 273 samples) for ternary beats (3_2 and 3_3). IBI's lasting longer than 3 seconds were excluded. Time-warping was applied to both **PH** and **PC** conditions, where jitter in the playback timing ($M = 0.002$ s, $SD = 0.003$) of **PC** rhythms warranted similar correction. Time-warped data were concatenated and cut to a multiple of 12-beat windows at 3.75 Hz (3.2 seconds) before DFT, spanning either 1640 (binary beat) or 1638 (ternary beat) samples per interval. Consequently for **PC** conditions, resulting DFTs covered 156.8 seconds (binary, 0.00638 Hz resolution) and 157.0 seconds (ternary, 0.00637 Hz resolution). **PH** interactions spanned on average 171.8 seconds (binary beat, $SD = 49.1$ s) and 163.0 seconds (ternary beat, $SD = 28.7$ s). Long, quantised windows minimised spectral leakage (Stergiou (2020)).

The spectra characterised neural entrainment at beat, meter, and subharmonic frequencies, encompassing both steady-state evoked responses (SS-EPs) as well as background noise EEG activity (Pikovsky et al. (2001); Nozaradan et al. (2012)). To isolate SS-EPs, a denoising algorithm (Mouraux et al. (2011); Chemin et al. (2018); Nozaradan et al. (2017)) subtracted average magnitudes of surrounding bins (6th–15th sidebands, ± 0.038 – 0.096 Hz for **PC**) from each frequency of interest, assuming local spectral similarity under absent steady state evoked potentials (SS-EP).

This noise reduction was applied both to **PH** and **PC** conditions with the same sideband consideration regardless of stretched duration.

However, due to minor frequency shifts caused by stretch interval variance (1638 and 1640 samples), the peak magnitude at frequencies of interest (0.625 Hz, 1.25 Hz, 1.875 Hz, and 3.75 Hz) is estimated as the maximum of the noise-subtracted magnitude from a set of three frequency bins centred over the frequencies of interest. Resulting peaks were assessed for significance above the zero and between conditions by Wilcoxon Rank-Sum tests, identifying DFT's overall characterisation potential. Additional Kruskal-Wallis tests confirmed the impact of condition on the shared subharmonic 0.625 Hz.

To assess entrainment strength, peak magnitudes were z-scored per interaction as $z = (x - \mu) / \sigma$, where x was the denoised magnitude at the frequency of interest, and μ, σ were the mean and standard deviation of denoised magnitudes across task-relevant frequencies and harmonics (0.625, 1.25, 1.875, 2.5, and 3.75 Hz) (Nozaradan et al. (2016a)). Present normalisation aimed to enable a direct comparison of neural entrainment across conditions by considering the presence of condition-related entrainment peaks along with lingering beat precepts of a previous interaction (Nave et al. (2022); Bouwer et al. (2023)). These z-scores were subsequently used in correlation analyses to link neural entrainment strength to individual subjective experience.

2.8.2. Autocorrelation frequency analysis

Given the non-sinusoidal nature of auditory and motor responses (Näätänen and Picton (1987); Shibasaki and Hallett (2006)), harmonic content was considered to capture an extended view of neural entrainment, (Zhou et al. (2016b); Kaneshiro et al. (2020)).

Normalized autocorrelation assessed periodicity in the earlier obtained time-warped AUD IC and MOT IC signals, aligned to fixed inter-beat intervals via stretching, similar to the DFT approach. This localiser data was denoised by subtracting an estimated 1/f noise component using Irregular Resampling Auto-Spectral Analysis (IRASA) Wen and Liu (2016), (`ft_freqanalysis()`, `fieldtrip toolbox` with custom parameters ('foilim' [0 256], 'pad' 'nextpow2', 'method' 'irasa', 'ouput' 'fractal'). To further suppress non-rhythmic oscillations (alpha and higher bands) while preserving beat and some harmonic content, stretched signals were zero-phase filtered using a linear-phase FIR low-pass filter (order 255), designed via least-squares minimization (`firls`, MATLAB). The filter had a 7 Hz cutoff with a 0.3 slope in amplitude decline, effectively reducing contributions from alpha and higher-frequency bands.

Autocorrelation was computed on filtered signals, focusing on local peaks for lags corresponding to the rhythmic structure of the stimuli (0.533 and 0.800 s for 1.875 Hz and 1.25 Hz, respectively). Due to the fixed resolution (1/512 Hz) and minor variation in segment lengths, the peak lag amplitude were taken as the maximum across the target lag and its immediate neighbours. Significance was assessed using Wilcoxon Signed-Rank tests (vs. zero), Wilcoxon Rank-Sum tests (between conditions) and Kruskal-Wallis tests to evaluate the general effect of interaction condition.

To quantify entrainment strength for correlation analysis, autocorrelation amplitudes were z-scored per interaction. Z-scores were calculated using the mean and standard deviation of amplitudes at lags corresponding to the target frequencies and their harmonics (0.533 s, 0.800 s, 1.066 s, 1.6 s; i.e., 1.875 Hz, 1.25 Hz, 0.9375 Hz, 0.625 Hz), allowing comparison across conditions and subjects.

2.8.3. Band Modulation

Event-related synchronisation (ERS) of beta-band power (18–22 Hz) was used to probe neural entrainment, particularly in relation to self-paced movement (Neuper and Pfurtscheller (2001); Rosso et al. (2022)). Beta modulation has been linked to temporal prediction, rhythmic tracking, and imagery of periodic stimuli (Fujioka et al. (2009, 2012, 2015); Kononowicz and van Rijn (2015)), providing insight into perception and attention. Although, during active tasks, interpretation must account for two complementary modulation sources: ERS linked to passive auditory onsets (Fujioka et al. (2012, 2015)) and event-related desynchronisation (ERD) associated with periodic motor activity such as tapping or walking (Rosso et al. (2023); Nijhuis et al. (2021); Borhanazad et al. (2024)).

To isolate beta-band dynamics, a linear-phase FIR band-pass filter (order 255) with a plateau between 18–22 Hz and 15% amplitude slope was applied (zero-phase; `firls`, MATLAB) as suggested by Rosso et al. (2022). A Hilbert transform was applied on the filtered signal to construct the analytic representation, from which the magnitude was squared to yield the instantaneous beta-band power. These signals were aligned to the interpolated phase of either finger taps (T) or constructed beats (B^*), with phase linearly increasing from 0 to 2π between successive events (Rosso et al. (2022)). Beta power was binned across 36 phase bins per cycle (Zhou et al. (2016a)), from it median values were taken to obtain phase-locked modulation profiles. A 2π -period sinusoid was fitted to each subject's phase-binned power, where

the amplitude of this fit quantified ERS modulation strength (Seibold (2024)). Additionally, the averaged rebound speed was estimated as $S = 2A/(T_t)$ with A being the amplitude and T_t reflecting the theoretical periods of the tapping task ($T_t = 0.8$ s and $T_t = 0.533$ s). Modulation amplitudes and rebound speeds were compared across conditions (2_2, 2_3, 3_2, 3_3) using Kruskal–Wallis, and between heard stimulus or executed task (binary vs ternary) via Wilcoxon tests. Cross-correlation between T - and B^* -aligned ERS profiles identified peak lag as an index of behavioural asynchrony.

2.8.4. Non-modulated band activity

Non-modulated band activity was analysed using standard EEG features to classify experience, complementing entrainment-based metrics (Cui et al. (2022); Liu et al. (2021)). EEG data from individual electrodes - after removal of non-brain components - were used, with segments from -50 ms to $+100$ ms around each tap excluded to eliminate muscle artefacts or anticipatory activity.

Electrode activity was band-pass filtered into four canonical bands (theta: 4–7 Hz, alpha: 8–12 Hz, beta: 12.5–30 Hz, gamma: 35–100 Hz) using linear-phase FIR filters (zero-phase, designed via *firls*, MATLAB), each with a flat plateau and 30% amplitude slope on both sides. For each electrode, instantaneous power was derived by squaring the magnitude of the Hilbert-transformed signal in each band. Total band power was then computed as the sum of these instantaneous values over the entire recording. Features were extracted from targeted lateral temporal sites (T7,FT7,T8,FT8), given their demonstrated relevance in emotion tracking and prediction (Zheng and Lu (2015); Zheng et al. (2019)). In contrast, frontal areas - though relevant for emotion prediction (Zheng and Lu (2015)) - were not included, due to their limited added value over lateral electrodes, as observed early in the analysis. Considered band-based features included:

Power spectral densities for each band j and electrode i , based on the total summed band power $P_{i,j}$ divided by the signal's broadband power content $P_{i,i}$ after muscle artefact removal.

Differential entropy (DE) (Gibbs (2010); Shi et al. (2013)), assuming a Gaussian distribution of values per band and fixed EEG segment length N .

$$DE_{i,j} = \frac{1}{2} \log_{10}(P_{i,j}) + \frac{1}{2} \log_{10}\left(\frac{2\pi e}{N}\right) \quad (3)$$

Differential asymmetry (DASM), providing additional information for emotion classification, (Davidson and Fox (1982); Lin et al. (2014)), computed as the difference of the mean differential entropy of the left (T7,FT7) and right (T8,FT8) hemisphere.

$$DASM_j = \frac{1}{2} \left(\sum_{i=(T7,FT7)} DE_{i,j} - \sum_{i=(T8,FT8)} DE_{i,j} \right) \quad (4)$$

Band Ratios (BR), given the theta–alpha and theta–beta ratios association with anxiety tracking and general relevance in classification (van Son et al. (2018); Zheng and Lu (2015)). Resulting features (DE, PSD, and BR) were then averaged across the four electrodes of interest and used along the differential asymmetry.

2.9. Correlates and Models

The markers of entrainment of Section 2.8 were correlated with self-reported, z-scored experience values. Additionally, behavioural synchrony and non-modulated neural activity served as baseline metrics for performance comparison. For this study, correlation analysis was limited to experience in *flow* and *pleasure*, given their relation to motivation during social interactions (Wilhelm (2017); Leman (2007); Puca and Schmalt (1999)). For each experience measure and feature set (behavioural synchrony, spectral frequency (DFT), normalised autocorrelation, beta-band modulation, and non-modulated band activity) two correlation models were constructed to account for task complexities. A "simple" model included data from conditions 2_2 and 3_3, while a "complex" model evaluated 2_3 and 3_2. Partner type (**PH,PC**) was introduced as a binary factor (*PC*), indicating a human (0) or computer (1) interaction. Multiple linear regressions (*lm*, **R**) were used to model the z-scored experience variables of pleasure and flow as a linear combination of the observed features, which included both partner type *PC* and one of the feature sets.

This modelling approach aimed to identify potential relationships between entrainment markers and subjective experience modulation. Each model was evaluated by examining the statistical significance of the feature coefficients and reporting the adjusted R^2 as a measure of model fit.

2.9.1. Classification Analysis

The predictive power of neural entrainment feature sets were assessed as well, and compared to that of behavioural synchrony or non-modulated band activity. An extended analysis, considering both correlates and their classification potential, can clarify nuances in present modulation of experience and the associated predictive power.

Here, each model consisted of a binary *PC* factor combined with features from one of the following feature sets: behavioural synchrony, frequency-tagged peaks (DFT), autocorrelation peaks, beta-band modulation magnitudes, or non-modulated band activity features. Predictive models were similarly constructed separately for simple and complex conditions. These resulted in five classification models per complexity for both pleasure and flow. For classification, the continuous z-scored experience value (z_{exp}) was converted into a binary factor (z_{exp}^*), where values above zero indicated improved experience relative to the mean, and values at or below zero indicated no improvement:

$$z_{exp}^* = \begin{cases} 0 & z_{exp} \leq 0 \\ 1 & 0 < z_{exp} \end{cases}$$

Using this binary outcome, logistic regression models (glm, family = "binomial", **R**) were constructed, predicting experience classification based on the same entrainment and baseline features. To improve model robustness and interpretability, each model underwent LASSO-based variable selection within a single feature set, using 5-fold cross-validation (cv.glmnet, alpha = 1, family = "binomial", nfolds = 5, type.measure = "class", **R**). Final models, consisting of a reduced feature selection, were then selected according to the 1-standard-error (1-SE) rule, prioritizing simpler models within one standard error of the lowest misclassification rate Hastie et al. (2009).

Selected features were used to fit final logistic regression models using generalised linear models (GLM) in **R**. Each final model performance was evaluated through statistical significance of individual predictors, Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), McFadden's pseudo- R^2 , and overall classification accuracy. McFadden's pseudo- R^2 , defined in Equation 5, provides a measure of model fit, with higher values reflecting an improved explanatory power relative to the intercept model (Equation 5). Here L_0 is the likelihood of a null model (no predictors) and L_M is the likelihood of the fitted model (Allison et al. (2014)).

$$R_{McF}^2 = 1 - \frac{\ln(L_M)}{\ln(L_0)} \quad (5)$$

AIC was also reported as a comparative indicator of model quality. Model accuracy was assessed using repeated random sub-sampling validation: the data were split into 75% training and 25% testing sets across 100 iterations. In each iteration, classification accuracy was computed as the proportion of correctly predicted outcomes in the test set. Final accuracy values reflect the mean across all iterations.

Figure 6: Topology of auditory and motor localisers. Electrode contribution heatmaps of auditory (left) and motor (right) independent components, averaged across 19 participants.

3. Results

3.1. Localiser topography

Following the procedure outlined in Section 2.7.3, auditory and motor activity was approximated based on the best-fitting independent components (ICs), extracted from dedicated auditory and motor localiser recordings. For the auditory localiser an across subject average of 124 (SD: 3.7) epochs were available for identification of the IC. On average, the identified auditory ICs accounted for 54.6% (SD:23.0%) of variance (pvaf). For motor activity, taps were extracted from the 190 seconds motor localiser with a pronounced increase in variability in available epochs (M: 281, SD:77.4). The selected motor ICs explained an average of 43.3% of the variance (SD: 25.5%). In 9 of the 19 motor localisers, the IC with the highest pvaf was not selected, as it did not match expected topographies or ERP features. Instead, the second or third highest IC was used. For these 9 cases, the mean differences in pvaf between selected and highest ranking IC were 11.8% (SD: 10.4%).

This discrepancy may reflect individual differences in cortical geometry (Cheng et al. (2022)), which can challenge ICA in isolating functionally distinct components. Alternatively, participants' hard taps may have caused acoustical leakage to the ears or electrode disconnection, limiting identifiability of the localisers due to contamination by auditory responses or malfunctioning electrodes.

Averaged scalp maps for both auditory and motor localisers are illustrated in Figure 6. The observed independent components showed clear agreement with literature findings in terms of topology and evoked responses for both auditory and motor systems. For the auditory components, observed responses were symmetrical in topology, agreeing with work by Näätänen and Picton (1987) along with a clear centralised activity around central-frontal electrodes FCz, Cz, Fz associated with the P1-N1-P2 auditory evoked potentials (Tremblay et al. (2014); Stropahl et al. (2018)). For movement evoked responses, topologies reflected a lateralized asymmetry, dominantly present in the centro-parietal regions agreeing as well with findings by Cheng et al. (2022); Gerloff et al. (1998).

Individual ICs that deviated from the averaged scalp maps were identified as outliers by considering per electrode differences in weighting to the average scalp maps. The absolute differences were summed across all electrodes to quantify each IC's deviation from the group average. ICs exceeding 1.5 times the interquartile range (IQR) were classified as outliers, and corresponding participants were excluded. For both auditory and motor localisers, participant ID9 was identified as an outlier and was excluded from further analysis.

3.2. Performance Markers

Table 3.2 summarises synchrony performance across conditions, using resultant vector length (R) and mean asynchrony (meanAS) as metrics. Participants showed significant greater synchronisation precision in the *simple* conditions compared to the *complex* ones. This was confirmed by one-sided Wilcoxon Rank-Sum tests for both R ($W = 646, p < .001$) and mean asynchrony ($W = 4242, p < .001$). Similarly, Levene's tests revealed significantly higher variability in the *complex* condition for both R ($F(1,156) = 28.3, p < .001$) and meanAS, ($F(1,156) = 13.3, p < .001$).

3.3. Effect of PC and COMPLEXITY on emotion

Prior to correlation analysis, the influence of task complexity and partner type were assessed. Interactions were classified as *simple* (identical rhythms: 2_2, 3_3) or *complex* (complementary rhythms: 2_3, 3_2). Figure 7 illustrates the effect of complexity on z-scored experience ratings. Wilcoxon Rank-Sum tests revealed significantly lowers scores

Condition	2_2	2_3	3_2	3_3
R (M)	0.88	0.39	0.38	0.86
R (SD)	0.11	0.27	0.29	0.13
meanAS (M)	-0.12	-0.01	-0.03	-0.02
meanAS (SD)	0.08	0.04	0.06	0.06

Table 2

Performance overview across conditions in resultant vector length (R) and mean asynchrony (meanAS).

Figure 7: Effect of condition complexity on experience. Comparison of z-scored questionnaire responses by condition complexity. Significance was assessed using Wilcoxon Rank-Sum tests; asterisks reflect p -value significance ($p < .001$ (***), $.001 < p < .01$ (**), $.01 < p < .05$ (*)).

in complex conditions for self-other-integration (Z_{SOI} : $W = 1298$, $p < .001$), agency (Z_{AGENCY} : $W = 1695$, $p < .001$), shared agency (Z_{SH_AGENCY} : $W = 1638$, $p < .001$), and arousal ($Z_{AROUSAL}$: $W = 4226$, $p < .001$). No significant effects were found for flow (Z_{FLOW} : $W = 3039$, $p = .87$), and pleasure ($Z_{PLEASURE}$: $W = 2685$, $p = .16$).

Figure 8 shows the effects of partner type - human (PH) vs. computer (PC) - on z-scored experience ratings, separated by task complexity. A Wilcoxon Rank-Sum test revealed significantly different arousal when participants interacted with a computer, ($W = 3808$, $p = .01$). No other significant differences were found in the ratings of self-other-integration (Z_{SOI} : $W=2901, p = .53$), agency (Z_{AGENCY} : $W=3252, p = .55$), shared agency (Z_{SH_AGENCY} : $W=2810, p = .34$), flow (Z_{FLOW} : $W=3492, p = .15$), and pleasure ($Z_{PLEASURE}$: $W=3290, p = .46$). When Accounting for complexity, partner effects on experience were limited to complex conditions (Wilcoxon Rank-Sum tests, 2-sided, $p < .05$), with significant differences for flow (Z_{FLOW} : $W=839, p = .017$) and borderline significant differences for arousal ($Z_{AROUSAL}$: $W=783, p = .079$).

Figure 8: Partner type effects on experience. Comparison of z-scored questionnaire responses by complexity and partner type. Partner differences were assessed within each complexity using Wilcoxon Rank-Sum tests; asterisks reflect p -value significance ($p < .001$ (***), $.001 < p < .01$ (**), $.01 < p < .05$ (*)).

Figure 9: Spectral peaks from discrete Fourier Transform. Normalised DFT amplitudes $X[n]/N$ (where X is the DFT coefficient and N the measurement length in samples) at motor and auditory localisers across conditions for $R > 0.5$. Significance of peak amplitudes (relative to zero) and auditory-motor differences was assessed using Wilcoxon Signed-Rank tests ($p < .001$ (***) , $.001 < p < .01$ (**), $.01 < p < .05$ (*)). Measurement counts and PC cases are shown in brackets.

3.4. Spectral and autocorrelation responses for auditory and motor localisers

This frequency analysis characterises the neural frequency spectrum during simple and complex synchronisation tasks by examining the distinct contribution of auditory and motor evoked responses across localised components. The analysis aims to highlight key differences in frequency content between conditions, offering insight into the core spectral features underpinning each task. For this analysis, only interactions meeting a minimum synchrony threshold ($R > .05$) were included, yielding 35 (2_2), 50 (3_3), 8 (2_3), and 9 (3_2) interactions.

Figure 9 illustrates the normalised spectral DFT components (0.625- 4 Hz) of both Auditory(Blue) and Motor(Yellow) ICs across all 4 conditions and Figure 10 presents the corresponding normalised autocorrelation. Coloured asterisks, indicate the significant activation (relative to zero) for each IC (Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test). Black asterisks denote the significant differences between the auditory and motor IC (Wilcoxon, Signed-Rank test). The DFT analysis revealed clear peaks at task and reference related frequencies and harmonics (2.5 Hz and 3.75 Hz) for both simple and complex conditions ($p < .05$), where peak significances were reduced in complex cases. Additional significant peaks were found at task-unrelated frequencies 1.875 Hz for the binary 2_2 interactions and 1.25 Hz and its harmonics for the ternary 3_3 interactions.

Subharmonics at 0.625 Hz (corresponding to a 6-beat measure, 1.6 s) were consistently present as well across all conditions in both the auditory and motor ICs. Few other frequencies showed significance, except for a peak at 2.1875 Hz in the motor IC. Furthermore, when considering all interactions ($R > 0$), peak significances were amplified for all condition-related components across conditions, though this introduces uncertainty on the present ability to synchronise and performed quality and is consequently not considered.

Autocorrelation results highlighted recurrence of the signal at 0.533 s, 0.8 s and 1.6 s for both auditory and motor localisers. In simple conditions, significant positive components were observed at task and beat relevant lags and at the 6-beat measure (1.6 s). Task- and beat-irrelevant lags (0.8 s for ternary and 0.533 s for binary) were either non-significant or negatively skewed. In complex conditions, reduced significant peaks appeared at 0.533 s and 1.6 s in both ICs, but were insignificant for 0.8 s regardless of the performed condition. In both DFT and autocorrelation, a 6-beat measure percept occurred consistently in the subharmonic at either 1.6 s or 0.625 Hz for both simple and complex interactions. Additionally, significance increased when considering low synchrony conditions as well.

To assess potential differences in this shared subharmonic (reflecting an underlying meter), Kruskal-Wallis tests were conducted across conditions. No significant effects were found of the condition in the DFT amplitudes (MOT

Figure 10: Recurrence peaks in Autocorrelation. Normalised autocorrelation of high synchrony trials ($R > 0.5$), evaluated at task- and beat-related time lags and subharmonics for auditory (AUD) and motor (MOT) localisers. Peak significances (relative to zero) and auditory-motor localiser differences were assessed using Wilcoxon Signed-Rank tests. ($p < .001$ (***) , $.001 < p < .01$ (**), $.01 < p < .05$ (*)). Measurement counts and PC cases are shown in brackets.

IC: $H(3) = 4.67$, $p = .20$, AUD IC: $H(3) = 0.48$, $p = .92$) or the normalized autocorrelation (MOT IC $H(3) = 0.85$, $p = .84$, AUD IC $H(3) = 3.05$, $p = .38$). Though consideration of the low synchrony interactions ($R > 0$), indicates that significant differences do occur between conditions in the autocorrelation (MOT IC $H(3) = 9.31$, $p = .025$, AUD IC $H(3) = 23.70$, $p < .001$).

To identify task-related modulation of entrainment under identical auditory input, Wilcoxon Rank-Sum tests compared subharmonic strengths between 2_2 vs. 2_3 and 3_3 vs. 3_2. No significant differences were observed in the DFT amplitudes (2_2 vs. 2_3: AUD IC $W = 637$ $p = 0.94$, MOT IC $W = 775$ $p = 0.10$; 3_3 vs. 3_2: AUD IC: $W = 1077$ $p = 0.17$, MOT IC $W = 939$ $p = .86$). However, significant differences emerged in the normalised autocorrelations: for 2_2 vs. 2_3 (AUD IC: $W = 457$, $p = .047$) and for 3_3 vs. 3_2 (AUD IC: $W = 1429$, $p < 0.001$; MOT IC: $W = 1217$, $p = .010$). Similarly, beat-related modulations for fixed task conditions, revealed no significant differences for DFT amplitudes (2_2 vs. 3_2: AUD IC $W = 603$ $p = 0.62$, MOT IC $W = 644$ $p = 0.97$; 3_3 vs. 2_3: AUD IC: $W = 960$ $p = 0.56$, MOT IC $W = 717$ $p = .12$) but did for autocorrelation for 2_2 vs. 3_2 (AUD IC: $W = 368$, $p = .001$; MOT IC: $W = 446$, $p = .02$) and for 3_3 vs. 2_3 (AUD IC: $W = 1259$, $p < 0.001$).

Evaluating the differences in internal representation between auditory and motor ICs, DFT amplitudes and normalized autocorrelation were compared at the condition-specific frequencies (i.e., the beat and task frequencies; see 3.4) by paired Wilcoxon Signed-Rank tests. Significant differences between auditory and motor ICs were found only in simple conditions: in 2_2 at 1.25 Hz and in 3_3 at 1.875 Hz for the DFT amplitudes. In 3_3, the normalised autocorrelation also showed a significant difference at a 0.533 s time lag.

3.5. Beta Modulation

Beta band modulation assessed frequency-specific alignment with external rhythms and self-generated movement. The analysis focused exclusively on motor ICs, given auditory ICs were affected by muscle artifacts that obscured reliable beta synchronisation patterns. Figure 11 shows beta modulation in the motor ICs for each condition. Blue lines represent oscillations binned to the constructed beat phase (B_n^* , aligned to the heard rhythms B_n), while the yellow lines correspond to bins based on tapping phase (T_n). Mean modulation magnitudes from the sinusoidal fits are presented in Table 3.5. Only interactions with sufficient synchrony ($R > .5$), were included here to ensure task compliance.

Wilcoxon Rank-Sum tests (2-sided) identified that the performed tapping task (binary vs ternary) significantly affected modulation strength for both beat-aligned (B_n^* , $W = 3716$, $p = .031$) and tap-aligned (T_n , $W = 3906$,

Condition	Frequency (Hz) / Timelag (s)	DFT W	DFT p	AUCR W	AUCR p
2_2	1.25 / 0.8	.005	**	.359	ns
3_3	1.875 / 0.533	.003	**	.009	**
2_3	1.25 / 0.8	.461	ns	.312	ns
2_3	1.875 / 0.533	.148	ns	.844	ns
3_2	1.25 / 0.8	.426	ns	.652	ns
3_2	1.875 / 0.533	.359	ns	.496	ns

Table 3

Comparison of peak amplitude between auditory and motor independent components for discrete Fourier transforms (DFT) and normalised autocorrelation (AUCR) by Wilcoxon Signed-Rank tests. ($p < .001$ (***), $.001 < p < .01$ (**), $.01 < p < .05$ (*))

Figure 11: Beta power modulations. Beta band power modulation of motor ICs in high synchrony trials ($R > 0.5$), aligned to the constructed auditory phase (B_n^*) or the self-tapping phase (T_n). Case counts are shown in brackets.

	B^*		T	
	Med.	IQR	Med.	IQR
2_2	0.018	0.034	0.016	0.037
3_3	0.007	0.026	0.009	0.026
2_3	0.003	0.060	0.003	0.064
3_2	0.009	0.026	0.006	0.013

Table 4

Beta band power modulation amplitudes, median (Med.) and interquartile range (IQR), in MOT IC across conditions ($R > .05$), aligned to either constructed beats (B^*) or performed taps (T)

$p = .005$) data. However, no effect of the heard rhythm was found for both alignments ($p > .05$). Across interactions, Kruskal-Wallis tests revealed a significant condition effect on modulation strengths for both for tap aligned ($H(3) = 8.91$, $p = .031$) and beat-aligned data ($H(3) = 8.35$, $p = .039$).

No significant difference were observed between the simple conditions (2_2 & 3_3, Wilcoxon Rank-Sum, 2-sided, $p > .05$), but for complex conditions (2_3 & 3_2) significant differences in both beat-aligned ($W = 456$, $p = .046$) and tap-aligned modulations ($W = 422$, $p = .016$) occurred. Additionally, rebound rates did not differ ($p > .05$) between simple (2_2 vs. 3_3) or complex conditions (2_3 vs. 3_2).

Finally, phase differences between beat- and tap-aligned modulations were evaluated via cross-validation but did not show significant delays, with phase offsets per interaction remaining close to 0 radians—likely due to the coarse phase binning.

3.6. Correlates

To evaluate the relationship between neural entrainment markers and subjective experience of flow and pleasure, generalized linear models were built within each marker set, analysing simple and complex conditions separately. In addition, classification models using LASSO-selected variables were constructed to predict subjective experience. Per neural marker set a table presents these full Gaussian models ("Gaus") including all variables, and binomial

Type	SIMPLE				COMPLEX			
	FLOW		PLEASURE		FLOW		PLEASURE	
	Gaus	Bin	Gaus	Bin	Gaus	Bin	Gaus	Bin
Acc		0.558		0.571		0.558		0.595
PC	ns	ns	ns	ns	-**	-*	-*	ns
R	ns	ns	ns	/	+**	ns	+**	+**

Table 5

Correlation (Gaus) and classification (Bin) model overview for the behavioural based models. Negative and positive coefficients are indicated with + and -, respectively, and features omitted by LASSO variable selection are indicated by "/". ($p < .001$ (***), $.001 < p < .01$ (**), $.01 < p < .05$ (*))

Type	SIMPLE				COMPLEX			
	FLOW		PLEASURE		FLOW		PLEASURE	
	Gaus	Bin	Gaus	Bin	Gaus	Bin	Gaus	Bin
Acc		0.618		0.571		0.612		0.558
PC	ns	ns	ns	ns	-**	-*	-*	ns
AUD_0.625	ns	/	ns	/	ns	/	ns	/
AUD_AUDTASK	ns	/	ns	/	ns	/	ns	ns
AUD_MOTTASK	/	/	/	/	ns	/	ns	ns
AUD_3.75	ns	/	ns	/	ns	/	ns	ns
MOT_0.625	ns	/	ns	/	ns	/	ns	ns
MOT_AUDTASK	ns	/	ns	/	ns	/	ns	/
MOT_MOTTASK	/	/	/	/	ns	+*	+*	ns
MOT_3.75	+*	+**	ns	/	ns	/	ns	/

Table 6

Correlation (Gaus) and classification (Bin) overview for DFT-based models. Negative and positive coefficients are indicated with + and -, respectively, and features omitted by LASSO variable selection are indicated by "/". ($p < .001$ (***), $.001 < p < .01$ (**), $.01 < p < .05$ (*))

classification models ("Bin") with the selected variables, along with coefficient significance. Classification accuracy ("Acc") reflects the average of 100 binomial model iterations using 75% training and 25% test splits.

3.6.1. Behavioural synchrony *R* correlates

In simple conditions, behavioural synchrony (*R*) showed no significant predictive value for the modulation of flow or pleasure. However, for complex interactions, *R* significantly modulated both experience dimensions in Gaussian models ($p < .05$). When classifying experience, *R* only significantly contributed to pleasure, not flow. Higher values in synchrony *R* were associated with an expect increase in both flow and pleasure for complex interactions, where PC conditions negatively impacted expected flow and pleasure.

3.6.2. Discrete Fourier Transform correlates

DFT Models were built using z-scored magnitudes from auditory (AUD) and motor (MOT) ICs at frequencies 0.625 Hz, 1.25 Hz, 1.875 Hz, and 3.75 Hz. Within each condition, frequencies linked to tapping task and heard rhythm were grouped as MOTTASK and AUDTASK respectively, for unified analysis (see Table 6). For simple interactions, the Gaussian models showed flow was significantly associated with motor IC activity at 3.75Hz (MOT_3.75, $p < .05$) and contributed to flow classification ($p < .01$).

Conversely, for complex conditions, pleasure was significantly related to task-specific motor activity (MOT_MOTTASK, $p < .05$), and similarly predicted flow ($p < .05$). Besides entrainment, a PC factor was included to account for observed non-adaptive partner's influence. Additional consideration of these models without PC confirmed this by absence of any remaining significance in neural DFT features in both correlation and classification models. Alternatively, other considered models such as behavioural synchrony, autocorrelation, and non-modulated band activity, obtained identical significant components in the linear and logistic models for both complexities regardless of the inclusion of PC.

Type	SIMPLE				COMPLEX			
	FLOW		PLEASURE		FLOW		PLEASURE	
	Gaus	Bin	Gaus	Bin	Gaus	Bin	Gaus	Bin
Acc	0.523		0.571		0.615		0.615	
PC	ns	ns	ns	ns	-*	-*	ns	ns
AUD_1.6	ns	/	ns	/	ns	/	ns	+*
AUD_AUDTASK	ns	/	ns	/	ns	/	ns	ns
AUD_MOTTASK	/	/	/	/	ns	/	ns	/
MOT_1.6	ns	/	ns	/	ns	/	ns	/
MOT_AUDTASK	ns	/	ns	/	ns	/	ns	/
MOT_MOTTASK	/	/	/	/	+*	+**	ns	/

Table 7

Correlation (Gaus) and classification (Bin) model overview for autocorrelation-based models. Negative and positive coefficients are indicated with + and -, respectively, and features omitted by LASSO variable selection are indicated by "/". ($p < .001$ (***), $.001 < p < .01$ (**), $.01 < p < .05$ (*)).

3.6.3. Autocorrelation correlates

Z-scored autocorrelation markers of entrainment were evaluated at 0.533 s, 0.8 s, 1.6 s time lags, regrouped into MOTTASK and AUDTASK labels. For simple conditions, no significant correlates (gaussian and binomial) emerged for either flow or pleasure ($p > .05$). Complex interactions showed motor IC activity at task-aligned lags (MOT_MOTTASK) significantly correlated and contributed to classification of flow ($p < .05$ and $p < .01$, respectively). Alternatively for pleasure, no significant correlates emerged for regression, though auditory activity at the 6-beat lag (AUD_1.6) significantly predicted classification ($p < .05$).

3.6.4. Beta modulation correlates

Beta band modulation magnitudes, aligned to both beats and taps in the motor ICs, did not significantly correlate with, or predict, either flow or pleasure ($p > .05$). Due to this limited presence of clear modulations in complex interactions, and general absence in the auditory ICs, the analysis omitted further consideration of correlates and classification.

3.6.5. Non-modulated band activity correlates

A set of non-modulated EEG features was included as baseline for model performance. Markers encompassed mean relative power (MEAN), band power ratios (BR), differential entropy (DE), and asymmetry (DIFF) across temporal electrodes (see Table 8). Significant correlates emerged in both simple and complex models, across Gaussian and binomial analysis.

In simple interactions, pleasure was significantly associated with theta-alpha ratios (RATIO_Theta_Alpha) and corresponding entropies (DE_Theta, DE_Alpha) ($p < .05$). For classification, relative beta power (MEAN_Beta) significantly predicted both flow ($p < .01$) and pleasure ($p < .05$), while pleasure was also linked to relative gamma power (MEAN_Gamma, $p < .01$) and theta-gamma ratios (BR_Theta_Gamma, $p < .001$) for pleasure specifically.

In complex conditions, flow was modulated by theta-alpha ratios and gamma asymmetry (BR_Theta_Alpha & DASM_Gamma, $p < .05$), while pleasure classification was supported by theta-beta ratios (BR_Theta_Beta, $p < .01$). Other non-modulated feature associations were absent in the complex conditions.

3.7. Model performance

Performance comparisons across the constructed models of experience are presented in Table 3.7.2, organised by interaction complexity and experience type. The table includes adjusted R-squared (R_{adj}^2) values from the full correlation models, McFadden's pseudo-R-squared (R_{McF}^2) and AIC for the binomial classification model.

Mean classification accuracies (ACC) are based on 100 repetitions of randomly split training and testing sets. The "ACC p" column indicates the one-sided Wilcoxon Rank-Sum test p-values, assessing whether each model significantly outperforms the behavioural synchrony (R) model. Models separately considered: behavioural synchrony (R), the Discrete Fourier transform components (DFT), autocorrelation (AUCR), beta-band modulation (BAND_B_MOD) and non-modulated band activity markers (BAND_ELEC).

Type	SIMPLE				COMPLEX			
	FLOW		PLEASURE		FLOW		PLEASURE	
	Gaus	Bin	Gaus	Bin	Gaus	Bin	Gaus	Bin
Acc	0.653		0.69		0.716		0.67	
PC	ns	ns	ns	ns	-**	-*	ns	ns
MEAN_Theta	ns	/	ns	ns	ns	/	ns	/
MEAN_Alpha	ns	/	ns	ns	ns	/	ns	/
MEAN_Beta	ns	+**	ns	+*	ns	ns	ns	/
MEAN_Gamma	ns	/	ns	-**	ns	/	ns	/
BR_Theta_Alpha	ns	/	-*	ns	-*	/	ns	/
BR_Theta_Beta	ns	/	ns	/	ns	ns	ns	+**
BR_Theta_Gamma	ns	/	ns	-***	ns	/	ns	/
BR_Alpha_Beta	ns	/	ns	/	ns	/	ns	/
DASM_Theta	ns	/	ns	ns	ns	/	ns	/
DASM_Alpha	ns	/	ns	ns	ns	/	ns	/
DASM_Beta	ns	/	ns	ns	ns	/	ns	/
DASM_Gamma	ns	/	ns	ns	+*	ns	ns	/
DE_Theta	ns	/	+*	ns	ns	/	ns	/
DE_Alpha	ns	/	-*	/	ns	/	ns	/
DE_Beta	ns	/	ns	/	ns	ns	ns	/
DE_Gamma	ns	/	ns	/	ns	/	ns	/

Table 8

Correlation (Gaus) and classification (Bin) model overview for non-modulated band features. Negative and positive coefficients are indicated with + and -, respectively, and features omitted by LASSO variable selection are indicated by "/". ($p < .001$ (***), $.001 < p < .01$ (**), $.01 < p < .05$ (*)).

3.7.1. Simple interactions

In simple interactions, the behaviour model (R_Z_FLOW) yielded a mean classification accuracy of 56% for flow. Compared to behavioural models, accuracy was improved ($p < .05$) in the DFT, band-based modulation (BAND_B_MOD) and non-modulated band activity. For pleasure, the behavioural models achieved a baseline accuracy of 57%, comparable to DFT, AUCR, and BAND_B_MOD, and similar to the intercept model. However, BAND_ELEC showed a significant improvement (BAND_ELEC, $p < .001$).

3.7.2. Complex interactions

In complex interactions, behavioural synchrony reached a mean accuracy of 55.8% for flow and 59.5% for pleasure. Flow classification was significantly improved across all four neural models (DFT, AUCR, BAND_B_MOD, BAND_ELEC; $p < .001$), with highest accuracies in BAND_ELEC (71.6%) and AUCR (61.5%). For pleasure, only BAND_ELEC ($p < .01$) showed improvements in accuracy, while AUCR showed a borderline significant effect ($p = .071$) not supported by AIC, indicating a lower model performance.

4. Discussion

The goal of the current study was to characterise neural entrainment in an active synchronisation paradigm and examine its relationship with emotional experience such as pleasure and flow. A specific focus was put on how this relationship differs depending on whether a person is interacting with a human versus a computer. A tapping task, incorporating both simple (waltz and march-like) and complex poly-rhythmic conditions, explored the neural workings of present entrainment and its relation to external experience.

4.1. Impact of complexity

To inform further correlates and classification models, analysis first considered how external factors — specifically, task complexity and partner type — impacted individual experience.

Rhythmic complexity significantly impacted multiple dimensions of z-scored experience. Simple rhythms led to increased self-other integration (SOI), agency, and shared agency, along with a reduction in arousal. Compellingly,

Neural Correlates of Human Rhythm Interaction and Experience

Model	Coefficients ($p < 0.05$)	R^2_{adj}	R^2_{McF}	AIC	ACC	ACC(p)
SIMPLE (Z_FLOW)						
Intercept					0.517	
R		-0.001	0.040	122	0.558	
DFT	MOT_3.75	0.027	0.069	118	0.618	< .001
AUCR		-0.034	0.007	124	0.523	.996
BAND_B_MOD		-0.027	0.017	124	0.491	1
BAND_ELEC	MEAN_Beta	0.021	0.087	116	0.653	<.001
SIMPLE (Z_PLEASURE)						
Intercept					0.586	
R		-0.005	0.000	122	0.571	
DFT		0.079	0.000	122	0.571	1
AUCR		0.031	0.000	122	0.571	1
BAND_B_MOD		-0.028	0.000	122	0.571	1
BAND_ELEC	PC + MEAN_Beta + MEAN_Gamma + BR_Theta_Gamma	0.110	0.311	107	0.69	<.001
COMPLEX (Z_FLOW)						
Intercept					0.521	
R	PC	0.153	0.072	97.3	0.558	
DFT	PC + MOT_MOTTASK	0.047	0.085	96	0.612	<.001
AUCR	PC + MOT_MOTTASK	0.122	0.120	92.5	0.615	<.001
BAND_B_MOD	PC	0.1	0.042	98.2	0.608	<.001
BAND_ELEC	PC	0.317	0.213	89.4	0.716	<.001
COMPLEX (Z_PLEASURE)						
Intercept					0.521	
R	R	0.145	0.11	93.4	0.595	
DFT		0.042	0.079	105	0.558	.990
AUCR	AUD_1.6	-0.017	0.103	96.2	0.615	.051
BAND_B_MOD		0.020	0.036	101	0.578	.810
BAND_ELEC	BR_Theta_Beta	0.0179	0.15	89.6	0.67	<.001

Table 9

Performance comparison of individual models, including behavioural (R), Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT), Normalised Autocorrelation (AUCR), Beta-band (BAND_B_MOD), and non-modulated band-activity (BAND_ELEC) models with listings of significant coefficients in each binomial classification model.

these findings for shared agency and SOI contrast prior work by Almaatouq et al. (2021), where increased complexity enhanced interpersonal synergy and self-other integration. Here, the clear change in paradigm setup from problem solving to behavioural centred interactions may limit the extension of these prior findings to a rhythm-based interactions.

For pleasure and flow, a clear influence of complexity was absent, diverging as well from earlier studies, including Stupacher (2019), finding complexity to modulate flow experience. Additionally for complex conditions, the first-beat emphasis was hypothesised to improve synchrony by offering a pronounced rhythmic template and likewise increasing entrainment (Repp and Su (2013); Van Kerrebroeck et al. (2023)). Strikingly, synchrony decreased, contrasting findings on rhythmic cues improving timing and entrainment (Carrer et al. (2023); Rose et al. (2021)).

Our results indicate that increased complexity may overwhelm performance, reducing synchrony, and reflect the context-dependence of complexity effects across different paradigms. These findings support the inclusion of complexity in the analysed models and classification efforts. Furthermore, does inclusion of complexity ensures that it does not confound or obscure underlying relationships between neural entrainment and individual experience.

4.2. Impact of partner type

Partner type had a significant effect on arousal and flow, though these effects were limited to the complex interactions. Specifically, interactions with a computer (PC) led to reduced arousal and flow, in line with findings from synchronisation paradigms using (adaptive) metronomes, which similarly impacted participants' experience (Fink et al. (2022); Mates et al. (1992)). These results also confirm prior research, highlighting the importance of partner flexibility in joint paradigms (Walton et al. (2016, 2018)).

The ability of a partner to collaborate and co-define rhythmic patterns, as discussed in Van Kerrebroeck et al. (2023), appears essential for fostering synchrony and positive interaction experience. Notably, the persistence of the partner type effects - even when controlling for complexity - underlines its relevance when assessing experience in synchronisation paradigms. Post-hoc analysis of synchronised trials ($R > .5$) further revealed that the partner effect on flow only emerged when synchronisation performance was sufficiently modulated across individuals. In other words, the experience-related modulation of partner type was contingent on synchrony modulation. This suggests that behavioural synchrony is a key mediator of how partner dynamics influence arousal and flow.

Our correlational models confirmed that behavioural synchrony modulated experience primarily in complex conditions, again suggesting the higher variation in synchronisation needed to detect such effects. This underlines the interdependence between synchrony, partner behaviour, and the subjective experience of an active interaction, and support the consideration of these metrics in future predictive models.

4.3. Neural entrainment characteristics

4.3.1. DFT and autocorrelation

To evaluate the relation between neural entrainment and experience, an initial characterisation of neural entrainment was conducted using both discrete Fourier transform (DFT) and autocorrelation (AUCR). Both approaches revealed condition-specific patterns of neural entrainment.

In simple interactions, DFT and autocorrelation consistently showed significant peaks at task- and beat-related frequencies or time lags, as well as their (sub)harmonics, in both auditory and motor localisers. These peaks replicate earlier findings on rhythm perception and performance (Nozaradan et al. (2017); Cheng et al. (2021)), and indicate that both heard beats and produced rhythms were neurally tracked. This suggests an internal representation of the performed condition across both auditory and motor regions.

In contrast, complex conditions showed weaker entrainment, likely due to reduced measurement counts when only considering well synchronised interactions ($R > 0.5$) combined with greater performance variability. The poly-rhythmic nature of these conditions may have distributed neural responses across multiple rhythmic components (auditory and motor), further reducing overall signal strength. Unexpectedly, DFT revealed additional peaks at condition-unrelated frequencies in simple interactions (e.g., 1.875 Hz in 2_2, and 1.25 Hz in 3_3). These may reflect carry-over effects from prior interactions, and relate to internal subdivisions or imagined beat structures, consistent with findings from mental beat tracking paradigms (Cheng et al. (2022); Nozaradan et al. (2011)).

Subharmonic peaks (0.625 Hz, 1.6s) emerged in both DFT and AUCR, aligning with an underlying 6-beat percept, potentially imposed by the initial audio-visual illustration. These peaks suggest perceptual grouping of the stimuli and top-down modulation of neural entrainment across conditions, as observed in previous work (Fujioka et al. (2015); Large et al. (2015)). However, despite the consistent presence of these subharmonics, there was no significant increase in neural entrainment at this frequency for complex conditions, although earlier hypothesised. This indicates that the more pronounced measure percept in complex interactions - due to the emphasised first beat - did not amplify perception of an underlying meter at 0.625Hz when properly synchronised, implying that top-down alignment to metrical structures is not solely driven by the presented stimulus and its synchronisation.

Still, it is worth noting that, in AUCR, the 1.6 s peaks may partly reflect aliasing from the subharmonic structure of the stimuli (0.8 s or 0.533 s), owing to autocorrelation's intrinsic properties. Therefore, recurrence peaks in the autocorrelation should be interpreted in comparison to the input signal for a refined view of the evoked periodicities (Lenc et al. (2025)), although this is challenged by the multimodal nature of both motor and auditory inputs.

Additionally, although a clear 0.8 s recurrence appeared in the 2_2 conditions its absence in both complex conditions - despite also including a binary component - suggests different recurrence contributions, even under good synchrony. This further underlines that normalised autocorrelation alone may not fully capture entrainment in complex interactions, given their absence of a 0.8 s time lag recurrence and additional limited definition of a single input signal.

Both DFT and AUCR showed similar tracking across auditory and motor localisers, with condition-matched peaks emerging in both regions. Differences in tracking magnitudes between localisers were mostly absent and indicates a shared content between both regions. This present overlap in activity between both regions underscores the integrated role of auditory and motor systems and supports the notion of entrainment as a multi-region phenomenon, not easily localised to a single source. Overall, although entrainment was reduced for complex interactions, it remained selectively significant at condition-related frequencies and lags, while being absent at unrelated frequencies. This reinforces the interpretive value of entrainment metrics and justifies their use in subsequent correlation analysis.

4.3.2. *Beta band entrainment*

Beta-band modulation was examined to further characterise neural entrainment within sensorimotor synchronisation, providing a frequency-specific lens on neural responses during overt movement.

For simple interactions, a pronounced event-related desynchronisation (ERD) in the beta band was found in the motor localiser, time-locked to both the auditory beat and the performed task. This aligns with proven beta ERD at tapping onsets (Rosso et al. (2022)), indicating a clear motor-related modulation. However, complementary event-related synchronisation (ERS) to periodic auditory stimuli, previously shown in passive paradigms (Fujioka et al. (2009, 2012)), was absent for the motor ICs. This could suggest either that auditory beta modulation is masked by the dominant motor activity, or that auditory-driven synchronisation requires auditory-localised regions for reliable detection in active contexts (Fujioka et al. (2012)). Additionally, given the temporal alignment between taps and auditory beats, observed ERD patterns may include muscle artefacts, complicating interpretation. As such, while ERD was consistently present for simple interactions, distinguishing whether it stemmed from motor, auditory, or artefactual sources remains challenging across conditions.

Comparison between simple conditions showed no significant differences in modulation amplitude and rebound rate between 2_2 and 3_3, despite visually indicative differences. These findings contradict earlier work on passive listening paradigms, where faster stimulus repetition rates affected post-stimulus beta power increases (Fujioka et al. (2012)) and interval production related to beta ERS magnitude. Furthermore, the visually elevated beta ERS in 2_2, although insignificant, could reflect interval production, consistent with work by Kononowicz and van Rijn (2015). This invariance of rebound rate mainly matched findings from Meijer et al. (2016), suggesting a beta band timing mechanism of prediction that operates invariantly of stimulus rate.

In contrast, for complex interactions, beta-band clear modulation was absent, and only ambiguous ERDs were observed for the synchronised 2_3 conditions ($R > .5$). This modulation reduction likely reflects decreased neural entrainment, as suggested by the small spectral DFT peaks and reduced behavioural synchrony. Accordingly, beta-band entrainment for the complex interactions was not further analysed, given the limited number of synchronised interactions and inconsistent band entrainment. Moreover, for the simple cases, with clear band modulation, no significant delays emerged between the beat- and tap-aligned sinusoids, potentially caused by the limited temporal resolution by binning, constraining a detailed timing analysis.

Summarised, beta-band entrainment emerged predominantly in simple interactions, reflecting motor systems engagement in the rhythmic synchronisation. The limited presence for complex conditions suggests the performance-dependent nature for neural entrainment tracking, where the split neural modulation between two opposing event related modulations (motor and auditory) further complicates a clear interpretation back to each separately. These findings underline the relevance of synchrony and the challenge in observing and shaping beta-band activity in complex active paradigms.

4.4. Correlates

4.4.1. *Behavioural synchrony*

Behavioural synchrony (R) contributed to both flow and pleasure, but only for complex interactions. This supports previous research where synchronised behaviour enhanced shared enjoyment and flow, (Fink et al. (2022); Leman (2007); Stupacher (2019)). The current study showed how synchrony modulated multiple experience dimensions, though experience classification was limited to pleasure, confirming its robustness as a marker of affective experience.

For simple interactions, synchrony was high with little variation, and did not show significant correlations for both flow and pleasure. This may reflect a low task-difficulty and challenge, not evoking sufficient emotional responses in pleasure or flow Leman (2007); Wilhelm (2017). Furthermore, despite the large spread in felt emotions suggesting

potential for synchrony-based modulation, the limited variation in synchrony further restricts predictive power. Consequently, classification by synchrony was limited to complex interactions with a mean accuracy of 59.5% for pleasure, moderately surpassing 52.1 %, indicating the potential further classification through neural features across complexities.

4.4.2. DFT correlates

Within the frequency domain (DFT), significant correlates to experience emerged only for motor ICs, illustrating the motor system's extended role in predicting experience beyond behavioural synchronisation. Notably, significant contributions from the auditory ICs were absent, despite observed reliance on both auditory and motor systems for perceiving and executing sensorimotor synchrony (Fujioka et al. (2012); Cheng et al. (2022)). Moreover, increased task performance links to an elevated internal representation of the auditory stimulus one interacts with (Obleser and Kayser (2019)).

Instead, motor-related frequencies and shared harmonics modulated experience (MOT_MOTTASK and MOT_3.75 Hz), limited to flow for the simple interactions and pleasure for the complex ones. Task related frequencies emphasize here the importance of motor-based neural entrainment for experience prediction. The considered self-oriented metrics indicate to be more dominant for experience correlations than external-oriented ones. These observations align with similar research, where a complex poly-rhythmic context drove cognitive attention inward, prioritising a self-centred embodiment over external auditory cues, Van Kerrebroeck et al. (2023); Burger et al. (2014).

Nonetheless, auditory frequencies may indirectly be reflected through their relevance in the construction of time-stretched EEG but may fail to appear independently. Motor aligned frequencies would then only be observed when synchronised to the auditory beats. Similar motor components predicted flow and improved mean accuracy relative to behavioural models, by 6% in simple and 5.4% in complex interactions. Here, despite added model predictors, AIC values confirmed increases in performance relative to behavioural-only models, highlighting the value of neural entrainment features - particularly those in the motor system tied to motor task, harmonics and indirectly the auditory beat - in predicting flow.

4.4.3. Autocorrelation relations

Autocorrelation measures, combining harmonic content into a unified recurrence representation, provided an alternative view into experience by neural entrainment. Significant correlates were only present in complex interaction for flow and limited to motor-related task components (MOT_MOTTASK). These components also emerged as significant predictors for flow modulation in complex interactions, reinforcing its predictive power.

Interestingly, for the complex interactions, auditory ICs (AUD_1.6) proved significant in predicting pleasure, despite lacking correlational support, indicating involvement of neural entrainment in the auditory system to predict experience. The presence of 1.6s time-lagged autocorrelations suggests that higher-order temporal structures, i.e., the 6-beat percept, play a role in further shaping experience, beyond task related components. This reinforces the idea that perception of higher order rhythmic templates, rather than motor tasks or auditory beats alone, informs affective experience.

4.4.4. Beta band relations

Despite clear relevance of beta band activity in timekeeping and synchronisation (Kononowicz and van Rijn (2015); Rosso et al. (2022)), no significant correlations were observed to experience in this study. This contradicts observed relationships linking beta activity to cognitive control and emotion (Fujioka et al. (2015); Liu et al. (2021); Adamos et al. (2016)), suggesting these markers may not generalise to active synchronisation paradigms. However, in complex conditions, the reduced neural representation of frequencies, may have obscured these relationships to emotion. Nevertheless, in the simple conditions, despite clear modulations, correlations and predictions remained insignificant.

4.5. Experience classification

Across simple conditions, neither behavioural nor neural entrainment metrics effectively predicted classification of pleasure, nor did they outperform a baseline model including only the partner type (PC/PH). In contrast, non-modulated neural activity (BAND_ELEC) outperformed both, attaining an adjusted R^2 of 0.11 with mean accuracies of 69%. Non-modulated models mainly included both beta and gamma band features along with their ratios to theta activity, corroborating earlier findings on emotional state decoding (Hang et al. (2024)) with emphasis on lateral temporal brain areas (Zheng et al. (2019)).

This illustrates that, when accounted for muscle artefacts, baseline oscillatory power (PSD, DE), ratios, and asymmetry (DASM) provided a high predictive value, indicating the extension to the neural characterisation of emotional states even in active paradigms. Note obtained accuracies for the non-modulated models are only indicative of their potential in active interactions, and do not reflect an optimized classification by non-modulated features.

Similarly for pleasure in complex interactions, neural entrainment showed no significant improvements to behavioural synchrony in classification. Only non-modulated band activity provided a clear increase in accuracy, with autocorrelation models showing borderline significant effects that did not improve AIC. Overall, when tracking pleasure, neural entrainment rarely outperformed behavioural synchrony features and, when it did, at a risk of overfitting, which limits practical applicability.

When predicting flow, both neural entrainment (DFT) and non-modulated band activity enhanced classification relative to behavioural models in simple conditions. Particularly, DFT entrainment markers - situated in the motor ICs at 3.75 Hz - improved mean classification accuracy by 5.4%, while also reducing AIC, indicating gained insight into experienced emotion and its prediction. However, non-modulated features still advanced further, exceeding DFT-based models by 3.4%. Though, this reduced gap in accuracy highlights neural entrainment's potential as a feasible alternative for experience prediction.

Complex conditions underlined the predictive value of neural entrainment when classifying flow experience. Multiple neural entrainment models surpassed behavioural synchrony, with DFT and autocorrelation models showing an enhanced AIC (96, 92.5) and accuracy (61.2%, 61.5%) respectively, each providing an additional 5%+ improvement to the behavioural metric-based model. Despite the alternative metrics for neural entrainment, the DFT and autocorrelation leveraged similar motor components (MOT_MOTTASK), with autocorrelation also including higher order harmonics.

Regardless, this double emergence of task-related activity in the motor ICs highlights its robustness and relevance as a marker of experience. Though, non-modulated features further outperformed neural entrainment, with a pronounced 10.1% increase in mean accuracy for flow in complex classification. This suggests that while additional insight can be gained from entrainment-based markers relative to behaviour, non-modulated EEG activity captures broader aspects of emotional experience for both simple and complex interactions. They illustrated an extension of the standard neural markers to active paradigms as well, highlighting their relevance.

5. Limitations and future work

It should be stated that the conducted analysis and observed correlates and relevant bands as predictors of experience should be verified in future research, as they resulted from available research on the neural entrainment and a hypothesised extension of the known attentional and cognitive modulation of brain activity combined with behavioural synchrony's ability to reflect experience. The results present exciting findings on the potential of neural entrainment features to explain active human-rhythm experience but may mask false positives resulting from the multi-comparison analysis framework. Hence, the analysis mainly served an exploratory purpose.

Furthermore, the temporal alignment of auditory cues and executed taps complicates the distinguishability between internal neural alignment and artefactual or muscle-based artefacts. Future research should ensure paradigms where artefacts are easily distinguishable from task-related alignment or provide sufficient artefact removal to ensure a clear analysis and less ambiguity, especially for band-based entrainment.

Lastly, no assumptions were made on the origin of the neural entrainment, be it a phase reset, imposed by the external environment, or relating to internal maintained oscillations which align to the outside world. The authors believe that, regardless of their nature as arguments towards either reasoning have been made, the present entrainment provides insight into the representation of the outside world and are hence analysed in this respect. Discussed results serve to identify correlates between internal entrainment and external experience without detailing its origin.

6. Conclusion

Neural entrainment - captured via discrete Fourier transforms (DFT), autocorrelation, and band-based modulation - exhibited clear condition-dependent variation of features in amplitude, allowing characterisation of interactions. These markers were more prominent in simple interactions, with reduced entrainment peaks in complex interactions, likely due to the reduced synchrony.

For classification, behavioural synchrony presented limited predictive power, with significant contributions only to pleasure in complex interactions. Alternatively, neural entrainment, especially in the motor components, effectively predicted flow and pleasure. DFT magnitudes at task-related frequencies and harmonics in the motor system consistently tracked flow across complexities, outperforming behavioural models. Autocorrelation further emphasised the relevance of the motor regions and additionally revealed the contribution of the auditory regions, particularly at higher-order subharmonic precepts, to predict experience of pleasure. This confirms H2: Neural entrainment can equal or surpass behavioural synchrony in experience prediction. Conversely, while beta band modulation was pronounced in simple interactions, it fell short of capturing experience across conditions.

Nonetheless, several significant components of neural entrainment emerged across the conditions, confirming neural entrainment's ability to characterise interactions and its value as a correlate and predictor of experience in synchronisation paradigms, hereby confirming our first hypothesis: H1: Neural entrainment can serve as a marker of rhythm interaction experience, where the magnitude of spectral neural magnitudes correlates with observed experience.

Lastly, although partner type (human or computer) had a less pronounced impact than expected, it consistently effected arousal in complex interaction, highlighting the importance of designing active synchronisation paradigms with adaptive and realistic partners to maintain engagement and ensure meaningful evoked responses. This confirms H3: Experience in a non-adaptive human-computer interactions differs from human-human interactions.

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8. Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT in order to improve conciseness and clarity. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

A. Appendix A: Null Effect of ID markers on z-scored experience

	Z_FLOW	Z_AROUSAL
Partner frequency (LM)	0.92	0.96
Partner relationship (LM)	1	1
MTI (LM)	0.96	0.97
Caffeine (WC)	0.82	0.99
Diag learning (WC)	0.94	0.93
Diag attention (WC)	0.97	0.79
Medication attention (WC)	0.91	0.96

Table 10

Overview of significance testing (p-value) for associations between pre-experiment questionnaire responses and z-scored post-experiment experience ratings. Ordinal variables - including partners frequency of meeting each other (`Partner meet frequency`), self-assessed partner relationship (`Partner relationship`), and the summed Musical Training Subscale scores of the Goldsmith Musical Sophistication Index (MTI) - were assessed via linear regression models (LM) with a single predictor. Presented p-values reflect the significance of the predictor's coefficient. Boolean variables such as caffeine intake prior to the experiment (`Caffeine`), diagnosed learning difficulties (`Diag learnin`), diagnosed attention disorders (`Diag attention`), and prescribed medication intake that can impact concentration (`Medication attention`) were evaluated via Wilcoxon Rank-Sum tests (WC) to verify their impact on z-scored experience.

B. Appendix B: Algorithm for Evaluating Performance

Cross luminance for both participants resulted from the shared performance (*perfgood*) between the participant in booth A and its associated rhythmic partner (PC/PH), evaluated throughout the interaction. Luminance was modulated based on *perfgood*: gradually increasing when *perfgood* = 1 and decreasing when *perfgood* = 0. The variable was updated throughout the interaction via a MATLAB script `updatePerformance()`.

Variable	Description
P1_N	Number of taps expected from Booth A
P2_N	Number of taps expected from Booth B
tlastgoal	Ideal tap timestamps (e.g., metronome, B*)
tlasttap	List of actual tap timestamps from Booth A
tlastP2	List of actual tap timestamps from Booth B
flag_pc	Boolean indicating whether partner is PC (true) or human (false)

Table 11

List of used variables

```

function updatePerformance()
% Compares tapping tempo and alignment of P1 to % metronome (for PC) or to P2 (for PH)

%% Settings
TAP_MARGIN = 0.100;
RATE_MARGIN = 0.050;
RATE_GOAL = 0.266; % Reference metronome (3.75 Hz)

%% Performance variables
perfgood = false;
Criterium1 = false;
Criterium2 = false;

% Amount of available measurements
P1_M = min(length(tlasttap),P1_N);
P2_M = min(length(tlastP2),P2_N);

%% PC interactions (PC)
if flag_pc
    % Check how closely the last tap matches the ideal reference (B*) timing
    D = abs(tlastgoal-tlasttap(end));
    if D < TAP_MARGIN
        Criterium1 = true;
    end

    % PART 2 Difference in tapping rates (referred to metronome)
    RATE_P1 = mean(diff(tlasttap(end-P1_M+1:end)))*P1_N/6;
    if abs(RATE_P1-RATE_GOAL)<RATE_MARGIN
        Criterium2 = true;
    end
end

%% HUMAN interactions (PH)
else
    % PART 1 find smallest offset in the last P1_N taps and P2_N taps
    P1_last = tlasttap((end-P1_M+1):end);
    P2_last = tlastP2((end-P2_M+1):end);
    [X,Y] = meshgrid(P1_last,P2_last);
    D = any(abs(X - Y) < TAP_MARGIN, 'all');
    Criterium1 = D;

    % PART 2 Difference in tapping rates (referred to metronome)
    RATE_P1 = mean(diff(tlasttap(end-P1_M+1:end)))*P1_N/6;

```

```

RATE_P2 = mean(diff(tlastP2(end-P2_M+1:end)))*P2_N/6;
if abs(RATE_P1-RATE_P2)<RATE_MARGIN
    Criterium2 = true;
end
end
perfgood = Criterium1 & Criterium2;
end

```

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